

Significance of Female Education in Economic Development

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ABSTRACT

Female Education in every sense is one of the basic factors of growth and development of a country. No country can achieve sustainable economic development without significant investment in female education. Education develops people's understanding of themselves and world. It develops the quality of their lives and leads to social benefits to individuals and society. Female education raises the growth and creativity and encourages entrepreneurship and technical advances. It also plays an important role in economic and social development and improving income allocation.

Keywords: Economic Growth and Development, Poverty, Productivity, Education, Technology, Trade, Health.

INTRODUCTION

Female Education is a powerful instrument of social change, and often initiates upward movement in the social structure. Thereby, helps to bridge the gap between the different sections of society. The female educational scene throughout the world has undergone major change over the years, resulting in better provision of education and better educational practices.

Not only does education benefit e person learning, but also the community in which they live. Education contributes to the economic stability of any given nation by increasing the income of the poor. Research has shown that no country has sustained consistent economic growth without a significant nation-wide literacy rate. In addition to economic stability, education promotes civil and international peace, as well as cultural tolerance and understanding.

Economics offers a variety of theories and models relating education to economic growth. Education increases an individual's earning potential, but also produces a "ripple effect" throughout the economy by way of a series of positive externalities

EDUCATION AND ECONOMIC GROWTH

Clearly the educational provisions within any given country represent one of the main determinants of the composition and growth of that country's output and exports and constitute an important ingredient in a system's capacity to borrow foreign technology effectively. For example: health and nutrition, and primary and secondary education all raise the productivity of workers, rural and urban; secondary education, including vocational, facilitates the acquisition of skills and managerial capacity; tertiary education supports the development of basic science, the appropriate selection of technology imports and the domestic adaptation and development of technologies; secondary and tertiary education also represent critical elements in the development of key institutions, of government, the law, and the financial system, among others, all essential for economic growth. Empirical evidence at both micro and macro levels further illuminates these relationships.

Offering girls basic education is one sure way of giving them much greater power -- of enabling them to make genuine choices over the kinds of lives they wish to lead. This is not a luxury.

IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATION IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Prior to the nineteenth century, systematic investment in female education was not considered important in many countries. Expenditures on schooling, on-the-job training, and other similar forms of investment were quite small. This began to change radically during this century with the application of science to the development of new goods and more efficient methods of production, first in Great Britain, and then gradually in other countries.

During the twentieth century, education, skills, and the acquisition of knowledge have become crucial determinants of female development and a nation's productivity. One can even call the twentieth century the "Age of female development" in the sense that the primary determinant of a country's standard of living is how well it succeeds in developing and utilizing the skills and knowledge, and furthering the health and educating the majority of its population.

An educated woman will also be more productive at work -- and better paid. Indeed, the dividend for educational investment is often higher for women than men. Studies from a number of countries suggest that an extra year of schooling will increase a woman's future earnings by about 15 per cent, compared with 11 per cent for a man.

Basic education provides girls and women with an understanding of basic health, nutrition and family planning, giving those choices and the power to decide over their own lives and bodies. Women's education leads directly to better reproductive health, improved family health, economic growth, for the family and for society, as well as lower rates of child mortality and malnutrition. It also fights against the spread of HIV & AIDS.

The past decades have seen extraordinary expansions in access to basic education for females throughout the African and Asian countries. Many countries are now on the brink of a further increase in access to secondary and higher education for females and in effecting spectacular improvements in the quality of education offered at all levels. As increasing numbers of females complete their basic education, their demand for education at higher levels is similarly increasing. Educating girls and women is probably the single most effective investment a developing country can make, whether or not women work outside the home. It creates a multitude of positive remunerations for families including better family health and nutrition, improved birth spacing, lower infant and child mortality, and enhanced educational attainment of children.

Countries in the Middle East are increasingly integrated in world markets for manufactured goods. Their ability to compete in these markets and in globalizing service markets will depend on the excellence of female development they bring to the competition. Ensuring that all citizens are educated and numerate, that many possess a wide range of problem solving skills beyond the basic level, and that some have world class professional skills will necessitate new curricula, improved teacher programs, and academic methods that encourage higher order cognitive skills.

Higher rates of high school and university education among women, particularly in developing countries, have helped them make inroads to professional careers and better-paying salaries and wages. Education increases a woman's and her partner and the family's level of health and health awareness. It can increase the level of resources available to women who divorce or are in a situation of domestic violence. It has been shown to increase women's communication with their partners and their employers and to improve rates of civic participation such as voting or holding of office.

Educated women are more likely to stand up for themselves, their rights and spend more time educating their own children and more likely to send both their female and male children to

school. She is more likely to initiate action for social change and better able to participate in decision-making and contribute to community or national politics. Educated women earn money “create more social change through organized and collective actions” (Moulton, J. 1997).

Educational attainment correlates to increased agricultural productivity. It is reported that “increased education for women would yield exceptional returns in terms of world food security. A World Bank study concluded that if women received the same amount of education as men, farm yields would rise by between seven and 22%. Increasing women’s primary schooling alone could increase agricultural output by 24%”. Education for women could also be highly effective in reducing the incidence of trafficking girls to brothels; increasing overall environmental awareness; and, reducing the likelihood of terrorism.

No country has achieved constant economic development without considerable investment in female education and their development.

If You Invest in a Girl, She Will Contribute to Economic Growth When She Becomes a Woman

There is clear and convincing evidence, amassed over the past two decades, that investing in female-specific resources in the areas of education, health services, reproductive health, and financial literacy leads to better educated, safer, healthier, and economically powerful adolescent girls. This can contribute to a substantially better future not just for the individual girls, but for their families, communities, and our world.

- Every year of schooling increases a girl’s individual earning power by 10 to 20 percent, while the return on secondary education is even higher, in the 15 to 25 percent range.
- Girls’ education is proven to increase not only wage earners but also productivity for employers, yielding benefits for the community and society.
- Women who have control of their own income tend to have fewer children, and fertility rates have shown to be inversely related to national income growth.
- Girls and young women delaying marriage and having fewer children means a bigger change of increasing per capita income, higher savings, and more rapid growth.

- When women and girls earn income, they reinvest 90 percent of it into their families.
- The impact of investing in girls is intergenerational. A mother with a few years of formal education is considerably more likely to send her children to school, breaking the intergenerational chain of poverty. In many countries each additional year of formal education completed by a mother translates into her children remaining in school for up to an additional one-half year.
- Women with at least a basic education are much less likely to be poor. Providing girls with one extra year of schooling beyond the average can boost their eventual wages by 10 to 20 per cent.
- An infant born to an educated woman is much more likely to survive until adulthood. According to a report, in Africa, children of mothers who receive five years of primary education are 40 per cent more likely to live beyond age five.
- An educated woman is 50 per cent more likely to have her children immunized against childhood diseases.

Women have made both direct and indirect contributions to this increase in productivity, growth and development of the nation. Women have a history of success as team players and problem-solvers. In surveys, female managers receive lower ratings on masculine attributes and styles of leadership (task oriented, directive) but higher ratings for non masculine styles (interpersonally oriented, participative), according to studies by Alice Eagly and her colleagues. In the past, when the masculine approach was most valued, this meant that women faced a substantial uphill battle in being (and being perceived as) effective leaders, although lab experiments showed women to be more effective when the roles were defined as less masculine.

More recently, however, there are signs of a change in the ideal managerial style, from one in which leaders sit atop a hierarchy and operate by setting objectives and rewarding those who are successful to one where leaders aim to encourage commitment and creativity and take on the role of a coach or teacher. Driven by an economic environment characterized by an accelerated pace of technological change and intense global competition, this apparent redefinition of the ideal suggests that women may now have a comparative advantage in key managerial skills that are associated with firm productivity.

Social networks inside the firm have also been shown to be important, both to women's advancement and to firm productivity, and women have always been good at building and maintaining these networks.

CHALLENGES IN FEMALE EDUCATION

The main challenges among girls to female education are:

- the cost of education – ensuring that communities, parents and children can afford schooling;
- poor school environments – ensuring that girls have access to a safe school environment;
- the weak position of women in society – ensuring that society and parents value the education of girls;
- Conflict – ensuring that children who are excluded due to conflict have access to schooling; and
- Social exclusion – ensuring girls are not disadvantaged on the basis of caste, ethnicity, religion or disability.

These challenges are not exhaustive, but they are recurrent themes in many countries. They constitute additional hurdles girls need to overcome to benefit from quality education.

CONCLUSION

The choices and opportunities available to adolescent girls will determine in many respects our global future: whether world population stabilizes closer to 8 billion or 10 billion; whether the Earth's environment is sustained; and whether the cycle of poverty is broken in service of prosperity and security.

Educating a girl changes her destiny, as well as those of her future children and ensures that she can contribute to the economic life of her community. It is imperative that the international

community summon the wisdom and resources needed to prepare, respect, empower and protect adolescent girls. Female Education is indispensable to economic development.

No economic development is possible without good female education. A balanced education system promotes not only economic development, but productivity, and generates individual income per capita. Its influence is noticeable at the micro level of an individual family.

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